

Metadata Cleanup

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Metadata Cleanup

1.1 Author

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1.2 Description

Fixing metadata cleanup for incomplete output files when jobs fail.

1.2.1 Problem

Previously, Snakemake did not reliably cleanup metadata for incomplete files. This meant that, the user had to either use `--rerun-incomplete` (to re-run all incomplete rules) or manually delete the flag files for the incomplete files (and had to decode the file hash). This was specially cumbersome and error prone in complex workflows.

1.2.2 Solution

This work item addresses this issue by allowing to clean the metadata for specific incomplete files from Snakemake's CLI.

1.2.3 Impact

This improvement enhances the usage and error debugging of Snakemake workflows, by allowing to clean the metadata of specific rules.

1.3 Associated Project Workitems

- [Issue 2933 - Error when cleaning up metadata when using workdir in snakefile](#)
- [Issue 3193 - snakemake --cleanup-metadata appears broken in 8.24.0 and 8.25.2](#)
- [PR 3405 - fix: cleanup of incomplete files](#)

1.4 Acknowledgement

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